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Trade openness and macroeconomic determinants of FDI reception in Latin America: a VECM approach

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Abstract

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is essential for greater integration into the global market and trade openness has become an attractive strategy to reach this goal. In this paper a model VECM is estimated to assess the trade openness impact and the main macroeconomic variables in the reception of FDI in Latin America along 1995-2018. Results highlight the market size is important and, trade openness is a necessary but not enough condition to attract more foreign capital. It seems to be necessary a major macroeconomic stability: low inflation, interest rate control and stable socio-politics conditions.

Keywords: foreign direct investment, vector error correction model, unit roots, trade openness, Latin America.

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Resumen

Apertura comercial y determinantes macroeconómicos de la recepción de IED en América Latina: un enfoque VECM

La Inversión Extranjera Directa (IED) es fundamental para una mayor integración al mercado global y la apertura comercial se ha convertido en una estrategia atractiva para alcanzar este objetivo. En la presente investigación se estima un modelo de corrección del error vectorial (VECM) para evaluar el impacto de la apertura comercial y las principales variables macroeconómicas en la recepción de IED en América Latina durante el periodo 1995-2018. Los resultados sugieren que el tamaño de mercado es importante y, la apertura comercial es una condición necesaria pero no suficiente para atraer más capital extranjero. Parece necesaria una mayor estabilidad macroeconómica: baja inflación, control de la tasa de interés y condiciones sociopolíticas estables.

Palabras clave: inversión extranjera directa, modelo de corrección de errores vectoriales, raíces unitarias, apertura comercial, América Latina.

I. INTRODUCTION

The foreign direct investment (FDI) attraction has become one of the main modalities of trade and financial relationship across countries. International trade theories emphasize the capital factor as the key element to increase the economic growth of countries. Therefore, FDI and its determinants has been attractive topic in economic research.

Over the last two decades the growth of foreign direct investment flows has been spectacular. According to World Bank data the FDI global flows in 1970 oscillated around 10 trillion dollars, while reached 51 trillion in 1980 and was 96 trillion dollars in 1990. However, since 1990, FDI has reported the most spectacular growth when it reached 1,461 trillion in 2000 (eight times higher than 1990) and more than 2,100 trillion by the year 2015. That is, during the last twenty-five years, FDI grew almost twenty times its initial level. In this context, the Latin American region has not been indifferent to this trend, also registering substantial increases.

Nevertheless, how much trade openness and macroeconomic factors in Latin America will have influenced the capture of FDI? why do the most economically strong countries in Latin America such as Brazil, Mexico and Chile attract more foreign capital? ¹ One hypothesis is that Market size (in terms of GDP), macroeconomic stability and trade openness degree have a positive impact on the attraction of foreign direct investment. Therefore, it is interesting to investigate the effect of the most important macroeconomic factors to attract FDI. It is even more important to know whether the GDP per capita, inflation rate, exchange rate, real interest rate and trade openness are or not determining the entry of foreign capital.

According to some previous studies, market size has a significant positive effect on FDI flows. Although the name of this factor for each study differs, all the investigations refer to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or GDP per capita (Ali and

¹According to own estimates based on ECLAC data, Brazil, Mexico and Chile account for more than 70% of the total FDI in the region.

Guo, 2005; Artige and Nicolini, 2006; Asiedu, 2006; Kolstad and Wiig, 2012; Ramirez, 2010; Mughal and Akram, 2011). For other studies, which use variables such as inflation, interest rate, exchange rate, mainly, is macroeconomic stability. In this line, the researches stand out of Froot and Stein (1989), Fischer (1993), Wint and Williams (2002), Xing (2006), Pradhan and Saha (2011) and Abbott, Cushman and Vita (2012), for which a stable economy is more attractive to foreign investors.

The trade openness degree is also a determining source of FDI (Campos and Kinoshita, 2003; No, Muhammad, Tamwesigire and Mugisha, 2008; Büthe and Milne, 2008; Mottaleb and Kalirajan, 2010). Generally, foreign direct investment is commonly made in open economies that offer above-average growth prospects for foreign capital.

This paper considers a panel data of seventeen economies over the period 1995-2018 and the variables GDP per capita, exchange rate, gross domestic savings, inflation, real interest rate, fixed capital formation and a trade openness index. The dependent variable is defined in two ways: FDI stock in absolute values and as a percentage of GDP.

The methodology used consists of unitary panel root tests and the development of a vector error correction model (VECM) to prove the follow hypothesis: the market size, stability macroeconomic and trade openness degree have a positive impact on attracting foreign direct investment in the Latin American economies during 1995-2018. The results lead to recommend the preservation of macroeconomic stability to make effective the potential sources of growth derived from a greater integration to the global market.

The outline of the paper is as follows. After introduction, we will present the theoretical framework of the determinants of FDI. Section 3 describes the trends of FDI in Latin America. The fourth section, the theoretical estimation model is exposed. The fifth section details database and the model estimates. Finally, we will discuss our findings and their implications.

II. DETERMINANTS OF FDI: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

II.1 Microeconomic factors of the industrial agglomeration

At first, the capital movements were related to the central place theories and its advantages. Among other authors, they stand out: Thünen (1948), Weber (1968), Christaller (1933) and Lösch (1957), who are considered as "the founders of location theory". Subsequently, the research line opened by Heckscher and Ohlin points out that the differences in the resource's allocation are the main responsible of capital movements (Krugman and Obstfeld, 2001). Hymer (1960) emphasizes the role of multinational companies. Through the imperfect markets' theory, the author argues there are two reasons for a company to internationalize, generating international capital mobility and increasing FDI flows. First, eliminate competition among companies, while the second is the reason to benefit of the competitive advantages that can be obtained abroad.

Kindleberger (1966) argues the technological innovation in a country generates a gap with other economies that accentuates the imperfection of the markets, leading to a successful internationalization. Therefore, capital flows are observed in the North-South direction from developed to developing countries. However, market imperfections are not enough to explain FDI flows, since the movements of capital international present barriers that many times do not make it possible to exploit the existing advantages in other countries such as macroeconomic conditions, the trade openness degree, and political stability, among others.

Dunning (1995) combines the Heckscher-Ohlin model, the industrial organization theory of Hymer (1960) and the imperfect markets theory to generate a more complete vision of the determinants of the international mobility of capital. According to the author, a company has three potential sources over its competitors abroad. Property advantages, that is, having tangible and intangible assets of the company (patents, innovative production and economies of scale). The advantages of internalization influence how a firm chooses to operate in a foreign country, that is, the company exploits its property advantage instead of selling it to other companies (reduces transaction costs by internalizing its own operations). Finally,

the advantages of location focus on the question of where a multinational company decides to locate itself.

Porter (2007) argues that the best way for companies to achieve a competitive advantage is their ability to innovate and improve themselves. The theoretical argument is based on four general attributes that all nations must take advantage of to have a competitive advantage: firm strategy, structure and rivalry, factor conditions, demand conditions and related and supporting industries.

The productive factors abundance does not represent a competitive advantage in international competition. For example, having a general workforce with a university education is not enough to compete (Porter, 2007), since the necessary demand conditions must be created for this purpose, be close to the producer and promote the interrelation between industries (productive chains). Nations trend to progress in the industries where management practices favored by the national environment are adequate for the sources of competitive advantage (industrial organization). A strong domestic rivalry and a competitive advantage are related. The closeness between the two stimulates rivalry between companies and this increases the competitiveness of local businesses.

II.2 Macroeconomic factors of attracting FDI

A considerable number of literatures on foreign direct investment highlight that the industrial agglomeration factors, such as the exploitation of a potential market of consumers, benefits, scale economies, the strategic location of firms inside a market determine the competitive advantage degree of a nation within its territory. However, these advantages reach a climax in which they lose strength when local market niches become saturated or overexploited. Thus, capital seeks to improve its profitability by taking advantage of the economic conditions existing in other nations.

Therefore, at the macroeconomic level, the relevant factors are: market size, trade openness degree that facilitates the capital movements and macroeconomic stability to impulse foreign investment flows.

Foreign direct investment depends of macroeconomic variables such as gross domestic product per capita, exchange rate and inflation, among others. Görg and Greenaway (2004) claims that the FDI receiving economies achieve "spillovers" that can be manifested through imitation, human capital formation and competition. Additionally, the economic development of emerging and developing countries depends to a large degree on the possibility of making profitable investments and accumulating capital. Having access to foreign capital and its investments allows a country to take advantage of opportunities to strengthen its economy (Ariel Gil, Lopez and Espinosa, 2013).

According to the researches, the macroeconomic determinants of FDI have been, market size (Ali and Guo, 2005; Asiedu, 2006; Artige and Nicolini, 2006; Ramirez, 2010; Mughal and Akram, 2011), trade agreements (Campos and Kinoshita, 2003; Büthe and Milner, 2008), trade openness degree (No, Muhammad, Tamwesigire and Mugisha, 2008; Büthe and Milne, 2008), the level of international trade (Mottaleb and Kalirajan, 2010) and the factors that inform on the macroeconomic stability, such as the exchange rate (Froot and Stein, 1989; Xing, 2006; Abbot, Cushman and Vita, 2012), inflation (Fischer, 1993; Wint and Williams, 2002; Pradhan and Saha, 2011), among others.

The market size of receiving countries is a determiner of the FDI since large markets tend to guarantee a higher return on capital. On the other hand, the more open is an economy in world trade greater facilities for FDI flows. Finally, a more stable economy guarantees confidence for foreign investors, while a country with economic instability sends signals of distrust to foreign capital.

III. FDI IN LATIN AMERICA: TRENDS AND DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

The main FDI receiving economies in Latin America are: Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Colombia, Chile and Peru (figure 1). Basically, these countries represent 85% of FDI inflows into region. Attracting around 30% of total inflows in the last years, Brazil proved to be the largest recipient of FDI in Latin America. Mexico is the second largest recipient of FDI in the region with nearly 37,681 million dollars in 2018.

Figure 1
Main receiving economies of FDI in Latin America, 2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

According to Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) in recent years Latin American countries have experienced a process of strong competition to attract foreign direct investment has led to a plethora of agreements that promote and guarantee the security of FDI, but the policy of trying to attract the largest volume possible shows some deficiencies. This competition involves defining investment schemes that ensure the greatest benefits for foreign capital, for which it is necessary to create conditions of attraction that, are above factors such as market size or the endowment of natural resources.

FDI had a rapid increase in 2007 and 2008, but the following year experienced a significant fall of around 40%. Despite the global crisis, FDI started to recover in 2010 and 2011 and, since then, FDI inflows in the region have remained stable (figure 2). According to ECLAC (2019), the factors that have contributed to the increase of FDI in Latin American economies in the last decade are the economic growth in the region and the high international demand for export commodities. Nevertheless, these conditions did not have a favorable environment since the region's GDP growth decreased to 2.5% and the exports price of the main commodities weakened slightly in 2013. However, investment decisions have not been affected and the region continues to receive large investment inflows.

Figure 2
Latin America: FDI inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

According to ECLAC (2019), not all FDI in the region represents a net inflow of capital. A very important component of FDI is the reinvestments profits of transnational corporations. World Bank argues that the profits reinvestments are

the main source of foreign investment resources in the region. Between 2005 and 2007, the profits reinvestments represented around 27%, while for the period 2011-2018 they reached 50%. Profits reinvestment may reflect the new realities of global capital markets after financial crises; but also, a perception of investment risk reduction by multinational corporations and their greater willingness to expand their presence in the region through a reinvestment process.

In 2018, the United States was the largest investor country in Latin America region (Brazil receives about 21% of the total FDI; Mexico receives 49% and Central America 30%). FDI from Europeans countries represents 46% of total investments in Brazil, 54% in Mexico and 36% in Colombia. Trans-Latin capital movements have been very important. Thus, 46% of total FDI into Ecuador comes from region, Central America (39%) and Colombia (30%). Asian countries have been constant in their investments, except in Mexico; of this region, Japan is the main investor followed by Korea. Both countries have large manufacturing investments in the automobile and electronics sectors. The main receiving countries of Asian FDI are Brazil and Mexico (ECLAC, 2019).

Investments in technology-intensive sectors account for a small proportion of total FDI, but they have more potential to contribute to development through knowledge transfers and increases in local capacity (ECLAC, 2019). By country, Brazil has maintained a trend over the period 1995-2018, which has allowed it to be the region main receptor, absorbing just over a third of total FDI (figure 3).

Figure 3
Brazil: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

Mexico is not the exception, along 2001-2006 was positioned as the first receptor of Latin America, which has made it attractive for foreign capital. Thus, FDI inflows shows a reasonably stable trend, unlike 2012, when country experienced a sharp drop in its investment inflows compared to the previous year. In the past decade FDI inflows toward Mexico was maintained stable (in nominal terms) reaches annual average of US\$ 23 billion. Reduction affected most sectors, but almost half of the fall can be attributed to a specific operation: the exit of 25% Santander bank shares of the Mexican stock exchange by 4,100 million dollars.

In 2013, FDI inflows in Mexico rocketed to US\$ 47.085 billion. The amount is more than double the previous year. This growth was due to the acquisition by the Belgian company Anheuser-Busch of 50% of Grupo Modelo in US\$ 13.249 billion (figure 4).

Figure 4
Mexico: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

On the other hand, Chile has become one of the South American economies with the most foreign capital flows. Since the historic FDI flows in 2012, there has been a decline in this country. Investments in Chile totaled US\$ 7.322 billion in 2018, which, despite being slightly higher than inflows in 2017 (up 19%), was still far short of the FDI received during the commodity boom between 2008 and 2015, when inflows averaged US\$ 21 billion per year (figure 5).

Figure 5
Chile: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

Over the last decade, Colombia has increased its importance for FDI. According to ECLAC (2019), investment flows show an upward trend. After world financial crisis observed a decrease of FDI. With inflows of US\$ 11.352 billion in 2018, Colombia was the fourth largest recipient of FDI in the region, even though investments declined by 18% compared to 2017. The oil industry was the sector that attracted the most FDI to Colombia and, despite contracting 18.3% compared to 2017, accounted for 22% of the total. The two sectors that received the most capital were financial services and mining, with FDI inflows growing by 19.3% and 76.1%, reaching a share of 17% and 15%, respectively (figure 6).

Figure 6
Colombia: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

According to ECLAC (2019), the repercussions of the fall in the international commodity prices in 2018 were felt in the level of FDI received by Peru, which totaled US\$ 6.488 billion, down 5.4% on 2017. This can be explained by the structure of Peru's exports, with mineral and metal products accounting for 70%, and by the fact that many transnational companies' projects are directly or indirectly linked to this sector (figure 7).

Figure 7
Peru: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

On the other hand, FDI inflows into Argentina totaled US\$11.873 billion, 3.1% more than in 2017, making it the third largest recipient after Brazil and Mexico. Flows have normalized since 2017, after the atypical levels recorded in the period 2012-2016 (ECLAC, 2019). Note that best year of FDI inflows in Argentina was 1999, with a total amount of 23,987.7 million dollars, almost 25% of total FDI in Latin America. This figure is related to the acquisition of the YPF oil company by the Spanish Repsol, which occurred in the first half of that year, which meant an FDI flow of 15,167 million, 63% of the total flows of the year (figure 8).

Figure 8
Argentina: foreign direct investment inflows, 1995-2018.

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the World Bank.

In last ten years FDI flows in Latin America have had upward trend. How has important this growth been for the region and the world? Most studies have diverse and sometimes not very clear explanations. For example, FDI has had positive effects on growth and development in some countries, while in other cases it has had negative effects (Edwards, Romero and Madjd-Sadjadi, 2016). Haveman, Lei and Netz (2001), based on a studies review, confirm that trade openness and FDI facilitate economic growth. Velde and Xenogiani (2007) find FDI encourages the development of skills in developed countries but raises international inequalities. Azman-Saini, Law and Ahmad (2010) find a positive effect of FDI, if accompanied by a development of the financial sector. If not the case, then there are no FDI effects. Choong (2012) claims FDI could stimulate or slow growth.

The impact depends on the degree of financial development of the host country. Other studies prove that there are null impacts, even negatives. For example, Ashoghian (2009) concludes FDI has no significant impact on the growth or productivity of the Japanese economy. Ghosh and Wang (2009) point out moderate and very small impacts in OECD countries.

Particularly, Mexico has monopolized large amounts of FDI and the annual average growth has been 2.1%, which represents an insufficient growth rate. Turner Barragán and Martínez Pérez (2003) analyze the reception form of FDI in this country. First suggests that FDI is very concentrated in some sectors; second, has created jobs, but has not contributed to raising its quality nor has it had the effect of dragging with the rest of the activities. De Groot and Pérez-Ludueña (2014) consider that not all types of FDI have the same impact. Given the importance of receiving FDI for growth, how important have the factors been highlighted by the theory in attracting FDI in Latin America?

IV. THE VECM MODEL: THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL DESCRIPTION

IV.1 The theoretical model.

Vector error correction model (VECM) allows dealing with time series data relating short term effect and long run behavior. The VECM corrects typical serial correlation problems and endogeneity among the explanatory variables. When variables of a model are non-stationary, the regression generate biased and inefficient standard errors, which means that the conventional criterion used to determine whether there is a causal relationship between variables is not reliable. Firstly, VECM suggests analyzing the unit root presence (non-stationary variables).

Supposing the series contains a unit root, it must be transformed to make them stationary, once they are stationary, the VECM can be applied. Therefore, it was decided to apply a VECM as they are useful for modeling time series in multivariate contexts where there are dynamic dependencies between the time series. They also present better results when there are more than two non-stationary series in the model.

One of the main reasons for choosing the VECM is the strong linear relationship between some independent variables. An advantage of VECM over traditional dynamic specifications is that multicollinearity tends to be lower since the

combination of variables in differences and in levels reduces the linear correlation, which allows a more precise estimation of the parameters.

In this paper, the unit root tests of Levin, Lin and Chu (2002), Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003) and Fisher's modified test (F-ADF) have been performed. In these tests, the null hypothesis suggests the series of the panel are integrated in order 1, that is, they have a unit root and therefore they are non-stationary.

VECM corrects the possible unbalances generated during series evolution process. Thus, the error correction model could be specified as (Greene, 2008):

$$\Delta \mathbf{y}_t = \beta_0 \Delta \mathbf{x}_t - \gamma (\mathbf{y}_{t-1} - \mathbf{k}_0 - \mathbf{k}_1 \mathbf{x}_{t-1}) + \mathbf{u}_t \quad (1)$$

Where \mathbf{y}_t is a endogenous variables vector and \mathbf{x}_t explanatory variables vector, Δ is an indicator of first differences variables, \mathbf{u}_t error term and the error correction mechanism is determined by $(\mathbf{y}_{t-1} - \mathbf{k}_0 - \mathbf{k}_1 \mathbf{x}_{t-1})$ which capture the \mathbf{y}_t deviations respect in its equilibrium value in the previous period. Coefficient γ takes values between -1 and 1 and indicates the magnitude of the adjustment from one period to another. The coefficient \mathbf{k}_1 is the long-term multiplier. It is the parameter that measures the long-term response of the \mathbf{y} vector in the face a change of the vector of variables \mathbf{x} . Finally, β_0 is the short-term variation.

Thus, the VECM hold back the information on the long-term relationships between the variables in levels, collected in the term of error correction, while allowing flexibility in the specification of short-term relationships, collected through the rest of the parameters.

Illustrating the model, assume the \mathbf{x}_t variable of order I (1) with a relationship with its long-term equilibrium (EQ_{LP}). For this purpose, we can say the relationship of this variable is in equilibrium and therefore \mathbf{Z}_t measures the magnitude of the imbalance, as shown in Figure 9, where short-term movements can be above or below the long-term equilibrium (EQ_{LP}). If it is above, the VECM coefficient will be

negative because it must go down to recover the equilibrium. Otherwise, when it is below, the coefficient will be positive, because it will tend to rise to resume the long-term balance.

Figure 9. VECM: Geometric representation

Source: own elaboration

IV.2 Empirical model

This paper has homogeneous information of 17 Latin American countries for the period 1995 to 2018. The variables analyzed in this study are: FDI (the stock reported by United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, UNCTAD), gross domestic product per capita, exchange rate expressed in United States dollars, inflation, domestic savings, real interest rate, gross fixed capital formation as a percentage of GDP and an trade openness index from the summation of real import and real export and divided it by real gross domestic product. Statistical information comes from the following official sources: ECLAC, World Bank and UNCTAD.

The VECM model estimation requires determining the endogenous and exogenous variables. Although a formal causality analysis can be performed, in this paper we focus in theoretical relationships and tests with VAR models to distinguish the

endogenous and exogenous variables.² For example, economic theory shows that FDI, domestic savings and gross fixed capital formation are highly correlated and can be controlled by macroeconomic policy objectives and, therefore, can be considered as endogenous variables. Such as, the flow (or stock) of FDI may increase if domestic savings and gross fixed capital formation increase.

On the other hand, FDI is likely to be reduced due to a decrease in both variables. GDP per capita, exchange rate, inflation rate, commercial openness and the real interest rate are considered exogenous in the model. In addition, the tests with VAR models carried out in this paper modifying the possible endogenous variables do not improve the adjustment obtained with the selected model, thus it decided the following VECM model:

$$\mathbf{FDIN1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{GDPpc, ER, INN, TOP, DOS, GFCF, RIR}) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{FDIN2} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{GDPpc, ER, INN, TOP, DOS, GFCF, RIR})$$

Where **GDPpc** = Gross Domestic Product per capita

ER = Exchange Rate (expressed in United States dollars)

INN = Inflation

TOP = Trade Openness Index

DOS = Domestic Savings

GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation as a percentage of GDP

RIR = Real Interest Rate

The empirical model considers the accumulated FDI and the estimated as capital stock. Thus, we work with two dependent variables: the FDI stock as a percentage of GDP (FDIN1) and the FDI stock in absolute values (FDIN2), that is, unused in

² Causality tests were performed but they were inconclusive to identify the endogenous and exogenous variables, so it was preferred to resort to theoretical reasons and estimates from VAR models.

relative terms. Both alternatives have been suggested in the reviewed literature on the FDI determinants.

V. RESULTS

V.1. Exploratory analysis

Table 1 reports some statistics of the study variables. Fisher's asymmetry coefficient is considered to study the heterogeneity of the distribution. Average FDI, exchange rates and inflation showed high positive values of asymmetry, 4.38, 3.35 and 4.21, respectively. The interest rate, gross fixed capital formation and domestic savings report asymmetry values close to zero, 0.39, 0.49 and 0.91, respectively.

Partial correlations show that some variables such as GDP per capita, trade openness, domestic savings, gross fixed capital formation and interest rate have a positive relationship with FDI stock (Table 1). Theoretically, an increase in the value of these variables should improve the FDI reception. For example, the positive relationship between saving and investment is explained because families save surpluses of their income, while the investment is mainly made by companies, the connection between both variables occurs in the financial market, where individuals and other economic decision makers offer savings and companies demand it to carry out their investments.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of study variables

	FDISTOCK % GDP	FDISTOCK A. VALUES	GDP pc	EX. RATE	INFLA	OPENNESS	SAVINGS % GDP	GFCF	INTEREST RATE
Mean	28.62	46741.20	4617.61	429.64	9.41	66.12	18.74	20.91	9.81
Max.	83.11	747891.20	16879.45	6424.34	99.88	198.77	42.03	36.07	93.92
Min.	3.08	293.00	699.51	0.18	-1.17	16.38	1.46	11.02	-86.86
Std. Dev.	17.34	102279.80	3415.70	1135.24	11.18	32.59	6.29	4.63	16.18
Asymmetry	1.14	4.38	1.24	3.35	4.21	1.14	0.91	0.49	0.39
Kurtosis	3.67	25.88	4.04	14.21	28.58	4.16	4.52	2.89	10.38
Partial Correlations									
FDISTOCK % GDP	1.00								
FDISTOCK A. VALUES	0.12	1.00							
GDP pc	0.28	0.47	1.00						
EX. RATE	-0.12	-0.06	-0.04	1.00					
INFLA	-0.05	-0.02	0.02	0.81	1.00				
OPENNESS	0.43	-0.26	-0.22	-0.06	-0.09	1.00			
SAVINGS % GDP	0.19	0.06	0.13	-0.06	-0.14	0.31	1.00		
GFCF	0.40	-0.04	0.11	-0.13	-0.12	0.64	0.52	1.00	
INTEREST RATE	0.05	0.02	-0.02	-0.81	-1.00	0.09	0.14	0.12	1.00

Source: own elaboration

The negative relationship that the exchange rate and inflation have with the stock of FDI is also observed. Theoretically, exchange rate depreciation discourages the foreign capital inflows, since it constitutes a weakness of the receiving economy. The same goes for high inflation rates. Interest rates changes are ambiguous in its relation to FDI given the null correlation presented. When the interest rate falls, the availability of cash is encouraged and consumption and, therefore, the demand for products are facilitated. On the contrary, a high interest rate implies cost money higher, which encourages savings and reduces consumption and economic growth. In this case, it is more attractive for entrepreneurs to save than to invest. However, high interest rates can also be attractive to foreign capital.

V.2. Estimates and results

Tables 2 and 3 report the unit root tests results. Table 2 shows the variables in levels, while the variables in first differences are observed in Table 3. All tests were estimated with a data generating process that includes intercept and trend. Additional trials that included only trend or absence of both, presented very similar results.

Except for trade openness and domestic savings, the variables have a unit root, since it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis in its version of levels (Table 2), while this is easily rejected when the variables are presented in first differences (Table 3).

Table 2
Panel unit root test (variables in level form).

Tests	Variables	FDI STOCK % GDP	FDI STOCK A. VALUES	GDP pc	EX. RATE	INFLA	OPENNESS	SAVINGS % GDP	GFCF	INTEREST RATE
Levin, Lin & Chu t*		-7.779 (0.000)	-5.081 (0.000)	-2.397 (0.008)	-3.698 (0.001)	-4.552 (0.000)	-0.328 (0.371)	0.577 (0.718)	-2.088 (0.018)	-3.133 (0.000)
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat		-4.590 (0.000)	2.230 (0.012)	-1.633 (0.051)	-2.944 (0.001)	-3.675 (0.000)	1.071 (0.858)	-1.082 (0.139)	-1.980 (0.023)	-3.292 (0.000)
ADF - Fisher Chi-square		88.328 (0.000)	64.850 (0.001)	45.274 (0.093)	57.701 (0.000)	87.895 (0.000)	28.600 (0.729)	57.355 (0.007)	47.456 (0.062)	84.538 (0.000)

Note: P-value in parentheses
Source: own elaboration

Table 3
Panel unit root test (first difference of variables).

Tests	Variables	FDI STOCK % GDP	FDI STOCK A. VALUES	GDP pc	EX. RATE	INFLA	OPENNESS	SAVINGS % GDP	GFCF	INTEREST RATE
Levin, Lin & Chu t*		-11.132 (0.000)	-9.937 (0.000)	-7.634 (0.000)	-13.141 (0.000)	-10.606 (0.000)	-12.709 (0.000)	-9.862 (0.000)	-15.909 (0.000)	-10.431 (0.000)
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat		-9.605 (0.000)	-9.676 (0.000)	-5.731 (0.000)	-8.371 (0.000)	-12.530 (0.000)	-11.286 (0.000)	-10.728 (0.000)	-13.202 (0.000)	-12.209 (0.000)
ADF - Fisher Chi-square		142.781 (0.000)	143.744 (0.000)	94.216 (0.000)	84.742 (0.000)	203.153 (0.000)	165.671 (0.000)	160.360 (0.000)	193.178 (0.000)	198.328 (0.000)

Note: P-value in parentheses
Source: own elaboration

The results for the first alternative of equation (2), FDIN1, are reported in Table 4. Trade openness is not significant, which suggests that opening foreign trade and increasing the external relationship (exports and imports) does not translate into a greater FDI attraction. Even though the exchange rate fluctuations can be harmful for an economy with large amounts of uncovered debt, the model estimates showed, foreign direct investment was not influenced by exchange rate. Note that exchange rate is no significant.

At least in this geographical region, trade openness and exchange rate control are a necessary but not sufficient factor for foreign investments inflows; other factors should be combined with the trade openness so that there is a greater flow of foreign capital.

This perception is additionally supported by the results of inflation and real interest rate, since the equations estimate a negative and highly significant coefficient. Therefore, FDI flows in Latin American countries could be stimulated based on improvements in macroeconomic stability. In recent decades, this region has been characterized by high inflation, continuous currency depreciation and interest rate management as an instrument of monetary policy.

On the other hand, the economies income level is negative and significant; however, when it is controlled by domestic investment (GFCF) the impact becomes positive and significant; a result that confirms the theoretical postulate that level of per capita income tends to stimulate the foreign investments inflows.

The estimation of this model shows the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship between variables. The coefficient of error correction indicates that the unbalanced is corrected at an average annual rate of 5% (Table 4). This value also indicates the FDI stock as a percentage of GDP was above its equilibrium value. Domestic savings is also significant; thus, the short-term unbalance is corrected by around 7% in a year.

Table 4. Results of VECM: FDI stock as a percentage of GDP

Regressors	Dependent variable					
	$\Delta \ln(\text{FDIN1})$		$\Delta \ln(\text{SAVING})$		$\Delta \ln(\text{GFCF})$	
	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value
Intercept	0.058***	(7.370)	0.011	(1.415)	-0.026***	(-4.191)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Openness})_{t-1}$	0.087	(1.572)	0.192***	(3.452)	0.261***	(5.949)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Inflation})_{t-1}$	-0.064***	(-2.726)	-0.004	(0.197)	0.006	(0.360)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Real interest rate})_{t-1}$	-0.044**	(-1.907)	-0.002	(-1.122)	-0.003	(-0.169)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Exchange rate})_{t-1}$	0.015	(0.871)	-0.094***	(-5.103)	0.044***	(3.076)
$\Delta \ln(\text{GDP per capita})_{t-1}$	-0.426***	(-7.132)	-0.125***	(-2.093)	0.395***	(8.334)
CointEq. 1	-0.056***	(-4.834)	0.020	(1.721)	0.005	(0.537)
CointEq. 2	-0.070***	(-2.479)	-0.122***	(-4.362)	0.059***	(2.675)
$R^2=$	0.28		0.17		0.35	
Cointegrating Equation 1	EQ1= $\Delta \ln(\text{FDIN 1}) - 1.318 \Delta \ln(\text{GFCF}) + 0.733$					
Cointegrating Equation 2	EQ2= $\Delta \ln(\text{SAVING}) - 0.750 \Delta \ln(\text{GFCF}) - 0.602$					

Note: *** denotes significance at 1% level.

Source: own elaboration

Table 5 shows relationship between FDI and its determinants using the stock in absolute values (FDIN2). The magnitude and direction are like those obtained with the model estimated results in Table 4. Trade openness and exchange rate keeps being a factor that does not influence on foreign investment attraction for Latin American countries, while the negative and highly significant signs of inflation and the interest rate, are indicative that macroeconomic stability is the main condition on foreign capital attract. In the same way, market size (measured as GDP per capita) is a fundamental determinant for foreign capital inflows. The cointegration equation indicates the absence of short-term unbalances that must be adjusted, since the coefficient was almost zero.

Although, in general, the estimated results of both models are too similar, a comparison between them suggests that second (Table 5) presents the best fit, according to Schwarz's information criteria.

Table 5. Results of VECM: FDI stock in absolute values

Regressors	Dependent variable					
	$\Delta \ln(\text{FDIN2})$		$\Delta \ln(\text{SAVING})$		$\Delta \ln(\text{GFCF})$	
	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value
Intercept	0.062***	(6.745)	0.013	(1.488)	-0.028***	(-3.912)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Openness})_{t-1}$	-0.042	(-0.750)	0.199***	(3.579)	0.251***	(5.791)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Inflation})_{t-1}$	-0.073***	(-3.059)	0.007	(0.332)	0.005	(0.273)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Real interest rate})_{t-1}$	-0.057***	(-2.388)	-0.000	(-0.013)	-0.008	(-0.317)
$\Delta \ln(\text{Exchange rate})_{t-1}$	0.025	(-1.344)	-0.098***	(-5.245)	0.037***	(2.528)
$\Delta \ln(\text{GDP per capita})_{t-1}$	0.392***	(3.679)	-0.129***	(-2.135)	0.375***	(7.932)
CointEq. 1	-0.005***	(-2.301)	-0.006***	(-2.434)	-0.004***	(-2.267)
CointEq. 2	-0.062***	(-2.329)	-0.111***	(-4.249)	0.058***	(2.867)
$R^2=$	0.23		0.16		0.36	
Cointegrating Equation 1	EQ1= $\Delta \ln(\text{FDIN 2})$ 8.508 $\Delta \ln(\text{GFCF})$ - 35.64					
Cointegrating Equation 2	EQ2= $\Delta \ln(\text{SAVING})$ -1.042 $\Delta \ln(\text{GFCF})$ + 0.288					

Note: *** denotes significance at 1% level.

Source: own elaboration

5.3 Impulse-Response functions analysis (IRF)

It is interesting to subject the variables to simulated shocks in some other variables, that is, to estimate the impulse-response functions (IRF's) from the estimation of the VECM models. IRF's analyze the reaction of contemporary and future variables to an innovation (or shock) assuming these limitations disappear in subsequent periods, while the other innovations remain constant (Hamilton, 1994; Gonzalo and Ng, 2001). FIRs show how variables return to equilibrium (Greene, 2008).

Figure 10 reports the each FDI measure responses used in this paper to the impulses in the other variables. The greatest reactions are presented to changes in saving and gross fixed capital formation. For example, a saving shock has a positive effect on FDI for up to two years, then it becomes zero and even negative. In contrast, the shocks in the GFCF were permanent and greater.

Figure 10. Impulse Response Functions Graph

Source: own elaboration

The rest of the variables generate very small impacts that fade out after two years average. The impulse-response functions confirm that macroeconomic factors have not been enough to stimulate the FDI inflows in Latin America.

The region governments should consider policies that improve savings and domestic investment to propel the foreign capital inflows since both improve the reaction response to FDI inflows, according to the impulse-response functions results.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The Latin American region, like other world regions, has been characterized by an international policy of strong trade openness as growth strategy and foreign capital attraction. However, FDI reception is not only achieved by opening the economy to world trade but also depends on domestic factors.

This paper shows FDI is highly dependent on market size in Latin America (larger economies capture greater capital flows, while smaller economies receive fewer FDI inputs) and the expected benefits of foreign capital, in terms of its effects to stimulate economic growth, are negatively affected if the country's macroeconomic conditions are not adequate. Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Colombia, Chile and Peru receive for 85% of total FDI in Latin America, while they are also the largest economies in the region almost by any other parameter.

For international capital, it is not enough for a country to reach a high level of world trade; this factor must be combined with macroeconomic stability conditions for capital to decide to locate in the region. Latin America's dependence on market size questions the ability of the other macroeconomic variables to comply its role of attracting foreign capital, while the region will continue to undergo from insufficient investment problems, low growth and low-income levels. Latin America has yet to improve its macroeconomic indicators (low inflation, interest rate stability, savings, and domestic investment) to improve its economic growth indicators, in a context where the globalization process involves competing for financial investment that generates jobs, which at same time increase the income of population.

Although the research focused on the macroeconomic determinants of FDI, it would be important to deepen the study and include political and social variables for the same period and obtain more consistent results from future research.

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